

**IMPACT OF DIFFERENT VARIANTS OF ANESTHESIA ON
NEWBORNS DELIVERED BY CESAREAN SECTION IN MOTHERS
WITH SEVERE MITRAL STENOSIS**

Rushana Doniyorovna Ismatova

**A student of 520 group of pediatrics faculty of Samarkand State Medical
University**

Samarkand, Uzbekistan.

Scientific supervisor: assistant A.A. Muminov

Purpose of the study: A comparative evaluation of the condition of newborns delivered by cesarean section (CS) in mothers with severe mitral stenosis (MS) using the traditional variant of general multicomponent anesthesia (GMA) and combined multimodal anesthesia (CMA) with mechanical ventilation (MV) based on epidural anesthesia (EA) with reduced concentrations of local anesthetics.

Materials and methods: We analyzed 38 developmental histories of newborns delivered by CS from mothers with severe MS (1.9-1.1 cm²). Depending on the anesthesia option that we used, all neonates were divided into two groups: the first one included 19 infants delivered under CMA with MV and based on EA with reduced concentrations of local anesthetics, while the second one included a similar number of infants delivered under GMA with MV. Both groups of mothers were identical in terms of gestational age (33-35 weeks), nature of surgical intervention, and degree of MS severity. The course of early postnatal adaptation of newborns was assessed using the Apgar scale at the 1st and 5th minutes of life, the Neurologic and Adaptive Capacity Scoring scale (NACS), and V.A. Bushtyrev scale scores at 1 and 24 h after birth. The heart rhythm of newborns was also assessed using cardiointervalography, and the tesion index (TI) was calculated at 5 min and 24 h after birth. The concentration of total cortisol (TC) in cord blood was determined using an immunochemiluminescent assay (ICLA) 5 min after birth. The

efficiency of spontaneous breathing was judged by oxygen saturation (SpO₂) at 2 and 24 hours after birth.

Results: The study revealed a less pronounced negative effect of CMA with MV and based on EA with reduced concentrations of local anesthetics in newborns. Under the conditions of epidural blockade application, the adaptation and adaptive capabilities of newborn organisms during the period of early adaptation to extrauterine conditions are preserved to a greater extent, despite the extremely unfavorable initial background. TI at the 5th minute after birth significantly exceeded the upper limits of the "stress norm," thus reflecting the extreme degree of stress of the sympathetic section of the ANS and the heart rate regulatory systems during the use of GMA with MV, whereas these indices were significantly less pronounced in newborns delivered under CMA with MV and based on EA with reduced concentrations of local anesthetic. In 24 hours after birth, TI in both studied groups significantly decreased, indicating the preservation of some disturbances in the regulatory systems of heart rhythm and sympathoadrenal mechanisms.

Conclusions: This study revealed a less pronounced negative effect of CMA with MV based on EA with reduced concentrations of local anesthetics in neonates compared to GMA with MV. This allows the recommendation of CMA with MV based on epidural anesthesia with the use of reduced concentrations of local anesthetics during cesarean section delivery in women with severe mitral stenosis